

Privacy-Preserving Directly-Follows Graphs: Supplementary Material

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Abstract. In this document we provide supplementary material description. We list the files attached with this documents and describe different attributes of each file.

1 Files Description

We evaluate the proposed model by studying the relation between its parameters: δ , ϵ , and MAPE. We use real world event logs for a better understanding of the relation between model parameters. We report the distribution of the risk parameter δ values, the distribution of APE values, and the distribution of ϵ across the edges of DFGs, for the experiments presented in the paper. We also report the distribution of the risk parameter δ across events.

1.1 Experimental Set-up

We implement the proposed model in python, the implementation is available on GitHub³. We perform frequency query by counting the occurrences of each edge. For the time difference queries, we subtract the timestamps of all the occurrences of every edge. The result is a distribution of values across every edge. We calculate the four aggregate operations: sum, maximum, minimum, and average across edges. The sensitivity of the aggregate operations is calculated as mentioned in the paper. We evaluate the system using 13 real-world event-logs. The used event logs and their properties are listed in the paper.

In the following experiments, we keep the precision parameter $p = 0.5$, which means that we consider attacker's guess successful if he gets as close to the true value as 0.5 of the maximum value. In a practical application, the user should decide which guessing precision is considered acceptable. In the following, we report the exact values of the experiments conducted in the paper to evaluate the system behavior.

³ <https://github.com/Elkoumy/amun/releases/tag/0.1>

1.2 from δ to ϵ and MAPE

In this setting, the framework takes the maximum acceptable risk level (δ) as an input, calculates the differential privacy parameter, ϵ , to achieve a risk level lower than input δ , and estimates the error level of the anonymized DFG after applying the ϵ -differential privacy mechanism. To study the effect of risk measure δ on the accuracy of the output DFG, we calculate the absolute percentage error (APE) over every edge. We report both the MAPE and SMAPE, as mentioned in the paper. We perform 10 iterations of experiments and calculate the average values across multiple runs. We report the effect of input risk level δ on both ϵ and error level, MAPE. The below files contain the value distribution of model parameters. The files could be found in the compressed folder.

- The file “**input_delta.csv**” reports the values of both ϵ and SMAPE for the input δ value. It contains average values across 10 iterations of the experiments. Table 1 lists the columns and their descriptions.
- The file “**input_delta_epsilon.csv**” reports the distribution of ϵ across edges for the input δ values. It contains 10 iterations of the experiments. Table 2 lists the columns and their descriptions.
- The file “**input_delta_APE.csv**” reports the distribution of APE across edge for the input δ values. It contains 10 iterations of the experiments. Table 3 lists the columns and their descriptions.
- The file “**input_delta_SMAPE.csv**” reports the distribution of SMAPE across edges for the input δ values. It contains 10 iterations of the experiments. Table 4 lists the columns and their descriptions.

Table 1: Column Description of the file “input_delta.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
delta	This column describes the value of input model parameter δ .
median_epsilon	This column contains the median of the calculated ϵ values of the entire DFG.
MAPE	This column contains MAPE value.
SMAPE	This column contains SMAPE value.

1.3 from MAPE to ϵ and δ

In this setting, the framework accepts a maximum error range as an input, calculates the corresponding differential privacy parameter, ϵ , to maintain it,

Table 2: Column Description of the file “input_delta_epsilon.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
delta	This column describes the value of input model parameter δ .
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
epsilon	This column contains the calculated ϵ value for this edge for 10 iterations of the experiments.

Table 3: Column Description of the file “input_delta_APE.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
delta	This column describes the value of input model parameter δ .
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
APE	This column contains APE value distribution across the corresponding edge for the input δ for 10 iterations of the experiments.

and computes the amount of risk associated with that error range. We use the MAPE to calculate the α parameter as presented in the paper. We report the effect of input error level on both ϵ and risk δ . The below files contain the value distribution of model parameters. The files could be found in the compressed folder.

- The file “**input_MAPE.csv**” reports the values of both ϵ and δ for the input MAPE value. Table 5 lists the columns and their descriptions.
- The file “**input_MAPE_epsilon.csv**” reports the distribution of ϵ across edges for the input MAPE value. Table 6 lists the columns and their descriptions.
- The file “**input_MAPE_delta.csv**” reports the distribution of δ across edges for the input MAPE value. Table 7 lists the columns and their descriptions.

Table 4: Column Description of the file “input_delta_SMAPE.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
delta	This column describes the value of input model parameter δ .
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
SMAPE	This column contains SMAPE values for input δ .

- The file “**input_MAPE_delta_per_event.csv**” reports the distribution of δ across events for every edge for the input MAPE value. Table 8 lists the columns and their descriptions.

Table 5: Column Description of the file “input_MAPE.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
MAPE	This column describes the value of input model parameter MAPE.
min_epsilon	This column contains the minimum calculated ϵ across edges of the entire DFG.
median_epsilon	This column contains the median calculated ϵ across edges of the entire DFG.
delta_median	This column contains the median calculated δ across edges of the entire DFG.
delta_max	This column contains the maximum calculated δ across edges of the entire DFG.

1.4 Execution Time Experiment

We report the results of the execution time experiment in the file entitled “execution_time.csv”. The columns description is listed in the Table 9.

Table 6: Column Description of the file “input_MAPE_epsilon.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
MAPE	This column describes the value of input model parameter MAPE.
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
epsilon	This column contains the minimum calculated ϵ across the events of the corresponding edges.

Table 7: Column Description of the file “input_MAPE_delta.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
MAPE	This column describes the value of input model parameter MAPE.
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
delta	This column contains the maximum calculated δ across the events of the corresponding edges.

Table 8: Column Description of the file “input_MAPE_delta_per_event.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
MAPE	This column describes the value of input model parameter MAPE.
edge	This column describes names of the edges as pairs of input and output activities.
delta	This column holds the distribution of the calculated δ across the events of the corresponding edges.

Table 9: Column Description of the file “execution_time.csv”

Column Name	Description
dataset	This column describes event log name.
aggregate_type	This column describes the aggregation function used (e.g., frequency for frequency-annotate DFG, average for average execution time difference, etc).
input_val	This column specifies the type of experiment, i.e. the value "delta" refers to the δ input setting, and the value "alpha" refers to the input MAPE setting.
parameter	This column describes the value of input model parameter (δ or MAPE).
time_diff	This column contains the execution time in seconds.